

**THE POSITION OF WOMEN-GIRLS IN THE SOCIAL-ECONOMIC
LIFE OF UZBEKISTAN (1941-1945)**

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Abstract: In this article, the role of Uzbek women in the socio-economic life during the First World War and the reforms implemented to increase the socio-political activity of women in Uzbekistan today, as well as the important measures taken to support women. It was said that it is important to study, analyze and develop the necessary proposals and recommendations taking into account our history and current situation in the implementation of tasks.

Keywords: Women, social and political activity, decrees, Women's State Committee, modern woman, national historical figures.

Introduction

From the time when humanity entered the stage of cultural and educational development of its history, the place of women in society has been treated with respect. Honoring women as a divine factor that ensures the continuity of humanity is the most basic article of the moral code of society. Such a respectful attitude towards women is not alien to the people of the East. But one of the important characteristics of the peoples of the East is that, until recently, women in the East were valued as the mistress of the family, the creators of new generations, and the teachers who bring them up, and this situation does not mean that they are cut off from the life of the society. It is known from historical sources that most of the women of the East are educated, knowledgeable,

enlightened people on par with their husbands, and they also participate in state administration. They opened a school in their homes or in the neighborhood where they lived and educated girls (and sometimes boys).

We all know that 1941-1945 was the Second World War, during which the role of women in the social and economic life of Uzbekistan underwent significant changes. As a result of the war, most men fought on the front lines, while women took on more responsibilities in home and work life. In Uzbekistan, women worked in the fields during the war years and contributed to agricultural production. They also supported the country's economy by working in factories and other industrial areas. During this period, women also actively participated in fields that were traditionally reserved for men. With the impact of the war, the role of women in socio-economic life became more evident, strengthened, and gained importance. This period was a turning point for the expansion of women's rights and opportunities and their active participation in the life of society in Uzbekistan.

During the Second World War, the socio-economic status of women in Uzbekistan underwent significant changes. As men went to the front, women began to participate more actively in the socio-economic life of the country. Women of Uzbekistan took an active part in agriculture, worked in fields and gardens, and ensured the country's food security. He participated in the production of plants and factories and contributed to the development of industry. The war years were the period when women began to take a more active role in the society and economy of Uzbekistan. Their participation in work and public life was recognized and appreciated, which helped to strengthen their role in society.

Thus, the socio-economic status of women in Uzbekistan during the war years showed their active participation in various fields of activity and served to strengthen their position in society.

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During the war years, the socio-economic situation of the women of Uzbekistan was very difficult and complicated. During World War II, while most of the men were fighting at the front, women were forced to stay at home to take care of their children and families. This situation has caused women to increase their responsibilities within the family and take on more of the economic burden. In Uzbekistan, women usually worked in traditional fields such as agriculture and housework. However, during the war years, women had to take on more responsibility and faced a greater workload in areas such as agriculture. At the same time, as the economic situation worsened due to the war, women had to earn additional income to support their families.

During the war, the women of Uzbekistan also experienced the consequences of the war. The devastation and loss caused by the war also took a toll on women. In addition, the famine and hardships experienced during the war made women's lives even more difficult. However, in this difficult period, the women of Uzbekistan showed their strength and courage. They did what they could to support their families and contribute to their communities. After the war, women played an important role in the reconstruction and development of the country.

Summary

In conclusion, although the socio-economic situation of Uzbekistan women was very difficult during the war years, they managed to survive this period due to their patience and strong will.

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